

” A STUDY OF PERSONALITY TRAITS OF B.ED STUDENTS ”

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ABSTRACT

Personality is made up the characteristic patterns of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that make a person unique. It arises from within the individual and remains fairly consistent throughout life. While there are many different theories of personality, the first step is to understand exactly what is meant by the term personality. The word personality itself stems from the Latin word persona, which referred to a theatrical mask work by performers in order to either project different roles or disguise their identities. It is the total quality of the individual's behavior. Individual affects other individuals through his personality. Thus personality is manifested in his various activities. In short personality is the total quality of behavior, attitudes, interest, capacities, aptitudes and behavior patterns which are manifested in his relation with the environment.

Keywords: Personality, Persona, Manifested, aptitudes, attitudes

INTRODUCTION

Personality also known as personology is the study of the person, that is, the whole human individual. Most people, when they think of personality, are actually thinking of personality differences - types and traits and the like. This is certainly an important part of personality psychology, since one of the characteristics of persons is that they can differ from each other quite a bit. But the main part of personality psychology addresses the broader issue of "what is it to be a person."

A brief definition would be that personality is made up of the characteristic patterns of thoughts, feelings and behaviors that make a person unique. In addition to this, personality arises from within the individual and remains fairly consistent throughout life.

Some other definitions of personality:

"Personality refers to individuals' characteristic patterns of thought, emotion, and behavior, together with the psychological mechanisms -- hidden or not -- behind those patterns. This definition means that among their colleagues in other subfields of psychology, those psychologists who study personality have a unique mandate: to explain whole persons."
(Funder, D. C., 1997)

"Although no single definition is acceptable to all personality

theorists, we can say that personality is a pattern of relatively permanent traits and unique characteristics that give both Consistency and individuality to a person's behavior."

(Feist and Feist, 2009)

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE

Education is a life living process. Education means all round development of the child. Through education one can take decision independently. With the help of education the power of thinking increases. One can improve his or her personality by education.

One's attitude toward challenges his/her face when seeking to achieve a goal or when trying to complete a task can help to determine whether he/she will be a success or failure in that goal or task. Having positive personal character traits will not only allow you achieve various tasks, but it also can be a strong indication of being a success in general.

In view of the above, the need of the proposed study is vividly clear and the study was quite justified to undertake. Therefore researcher decided to conduct the research on the topic mentioned below-

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

“A Study Of Personality Traits Of B.Ed Students”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The study was designed to achieve the following objectives:-

1. To study the Personality traits of B.Ed students.

2. To study the Personality traits of B.Ed girls students.
3. To study the personality traits of B.Ed. Boys students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

To achieve the objectives of the present study the following hypotheses were formulated:

1. There is no significant difference exists between Personality traits of B.Ed boys students.
2. There is no significant difference exists between Personality traits of B.Ed girls students.

METHOD OF RESEARCH:

The researcher proposes random purposive method for the study.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY:

B.Ed students of a self finance college situated in Ghaziabad district of UP will comprise population of the study.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

A sample is small proportion selected for observation and anylysis. By observing the characteristic of the sample, one can make certain inferences about the characteristics of the population from which it is drawn. The essential requirement of any sample is that it is representative of the population. Miller (1977) states the scope of generalization of the findings depend on the representativeness of the whole population.

In the present study 10 students will be selected randomly as the sample of the study including both boys and girls.

TOOLS USED FOR RESEARCH:

Researcher will be used some questions from personality tool 16PF (by RB Cattell's)) for collecting the data regarding the research accordingly.

Major Findings of the study:

A person might have a dash of openness, a lot of conscientiousness, an average amount of extraversion, plenty of agreeableness and almost no neuroticism at all. Or someone could be disagreeable, neurotic, introverted, conscientious and hardly open at all.

Conclusion:

The present study indicates different types of personality traits of B.Ed. students. More or less their family circumstances and nature of course is affecting them.

Openness

Openness is shorthand for "openness to experience." People who are high in openness enjoy adventure. They're curious and appreciate art, imagination and new things. The motto of the open individual might be "Variety is the spice of life."

People low in openness is just the opposite: They prefer to stick to their habits, avoid new experiences and probably aren't the most adventurous eaters. Changing personality is usually considered a tough process, but openness is a personality trait that's been shown to be subject to change in adulthood. In a 2011 study, people who took psilocybin, or hallucinogenic became more open after the experience. The effect lasted at least a year, suggesting that it might be permanent.

Speaking of experimental drug use, California's try-anything culture is no myth. A study of personality traits across the United States released in 2013 found that openness is most prevalent on the West Coast.

Conscientiousness

People who are conscientious are organized and have a strong sense of duty. They're dependable, disciplined and achievement-focused. You won't find conscientious types jetting off on round-the-world journeys with only a backpack; they're planners.

People low in conscientiousness are more spontaneous and freewheeling. They may tend toward carelessness. Conscientiousness is a helpful trait to have, as it has been linked to achievement in school and on the job.

Extraversion

Extraversion versus introversion is possibly the most recognizable personality trait of the Big Five. The more of an extravert someone is, the more of a social butterfly they are. Extraverts are chatty, sociable and draw energy from crowds. They tend to be assertive and cheerful in their social interactions.

Introverts, on the other hand, need plenty of alone time, perhaps because their brains process social interaction differently. Introversion is often confused with shyness, but the two aren't the same. Shyness implies a fear of social interactions or an inability to function socially. Introverts can be perfectly charming at parties — they just prefer solo or small-group activities.

Agreeableness

Agreeableness measures the extent of a person's warmth and kindness. The more agreeable someone is, the more likely they are to be trusting, helpful and compassionate. Disagreeable people are cold and suspicious of others, and they're less likely to cooperate.

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